

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Domain Introduction

Networking is used to interact with others to exchange information. Computer networks can be linked through wires, cables, telephone lines.. etc. Router plays a vital role in the concept of networking because it identifies all the computer nodes present in a network and assigns various address for each node that address is called as an IP address.

1.2 Problem Definition

Each user is able to define his/her privacy policy and exposure policy. Only when a photo is processed with owner's privacy policy and co-owner's exposure policy could it be posted. However, the co-owners of a co-photo cannot be determined automatically, instead, potential co-owners could only be identified by using the tagging features on the current OSNs.

1.3 Project Description

To prevent possible privacy leakage of a photo, each individual in a photo be aware of the posting activity and participate in the decision making on the posting and tagging. If a request is sent to another person it will show the matches and mismatches. Then for user tagging or adding to group it will not automatically tag it will ask for the permission from the user.

The main aim is to give privacy to the people who has been involved in their respective social network, if the user tag someone photo then the user has upload their details first they will get the notification and if he / she wish to proceed he can visit but that cannot be viewed by anyone in his /her friends list.

If the user has sent request the another person that request has been received by the server database it also have other persons request then the request that has been received by the person his / her wish can add the friend in their list. Before this the people those who are not involved in the corresponding applications. If they need they can enter their basic information details of ones individuals. They have to update the profile picture. There is no restriction in sharing the co-photos.

The photos can be shared but they need to ask the permission of co-owners. Otherwise privacy violation may occur. The user has to send the request then if another person accept he can add his / her in the friends list. For example, in schools and in colleges the person name is same as to another person. Then the person can get the particular information of another person. The person can get the available details of another person who has requested to him. The details of the user stored in the database can be matched by profile matching algorithm.

The users can be either wish he / she can accept him / his friend in the list. The person can able to accept in the friend list .The main aim is to provide the privacy to the individuals those who are in the social network.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

PAPER 1

Title: Enabling Privacy-preserving Image-centric Social Discovery

Author: Xingliang Yuan, Xinyu Wang, Cong Wang, Anna Squicciarini,
and Kui Ren

Year: 2014

Explanation:

The increasing popularity of images at social media sites is posing new opportunities for social discovery applications, i.e., suggesting new friends and discovering new social groups with similar interests via exploring images. To effectively handle the explosive growth of images involved in social discovery, one common trend for many emerging social media sites is to leverage the commercial public cloud as their robust backend datacenter. While extremely convenient, directly exposing content-rich images and the related social discovery results to the public cloud also raises new acute privacy concerns. In light of the observation, a privacy-preserving social discovery service architecture based on encrypted images. As the core of such social discovery is to compare and quantify similar images, first adopt the effective Bag-of-Words model to extract the “visual similarity content” of users’ images into image profile vectors, and then model the problem as similarity retrieval of encrypted high-dimensional image profiles

PAPER 2

Title: Social Discovery: Exploring the Correlation Among Three-Dimensional Social Relationships.

Author: Hongyang Zhao, Huan Zhou, Chengjue Yuan, Yinghua Huang, Jiming Chen.

Year:2015

Explanation:

The correlation among three kinds of social relationships: face-to-face social relationship, online social relationship, and self-report social relationship. An experiment was carried out to collect users' three-dimensional social data: real-world mobile trace data, virtual-world online social data, and self-report social data. By analyzing network structure, we find that friendship in online social networks can better describe self-report friendship compared to friendship created by frequent physical encounters. Several supervised classifiers with the combination of features extracted from mobile trace data and online social data are used to predict the self-report social relationship under different social strengths. Results show that the proposed model can correctly predict more than 80% friends under strongest social tie strength. What is more, social popularity according to social relationships self-reported by users. By comparing social popularity with online and offline social behaviors, we find diversity in weekend is a good measure to describe social popularity.

PAPER 3

Title: Exploiting Social Ties for Cooperative D2D Communications: A MobileSocial Networking Case

Author: Xu Chen, Brian Proulx, Xiaowen Gong and Junshan Zhang

Year: 2014

Explanation:

The convergence of pervasive mobile communications and fast-growing online social networking, mobile social networking is penetrating into our everyday life. Aiming to develop a systematic understanding of mobile social networks, exploit social ties in human social networks to enhance cooperative device-to-device (D2D) communications. Specifically, as handheld devices are carried by human beings, we leverage two key social phenomena, namely social trust and social reciprocity, to promote efficient cooperation among devices. With this insight, develop an coalitional game-theoretic framework to devise social- tie-based cooperation strategies for D2D communications. Also develop a network-assisted relay selection mechanism to implement the coalitional game solution, and show that the mechanism is immune to group deviations, individually rational, truthful, and computationally efficient. We evaluate the performance of the mechanism by using real social data traces. Simulation results corroborate that the proposed mechanism can achieve significant performance gain over the case without D2D cooperation.

PAPER 4

Title: On the Interplay Between Individuals' Evolving Interaction Patterns and Traits in Dynamic Multiplex Social Networks

Author: Lei Meng, Yuriy Hulovatyy, Aaron Striegel, and Tijana Milenkovi

Year: 2016

Explanation:

The interplay between individuals' social interactions and traits has been studied extensively but traditionally from static or homogeneous social network perspectives. The recent availability of dynamic and heterogeneous (multiplex) network data has introduced a variety of new challenges. Critically, novel computational models are needed that can cope with data dynamics and heterogeneity. A computational framework that is broadly applicable to a variety of dynamic, multiplex domains, which focuses on: 1) measuring changes in node interaction patterns with time, 2) clustering nodes with similar evolving patterns, and 3) linking the clusters with trait similarities. The framework is applied to study the interplay between evolving topology and traits in an 18-month social network dataset encompassing both digital communications and co-location instances. In addition, uncover network-trait interplays that have not been studied to date and could lead to novel insights by domain scientists.

PAPER 5

Title: Constructing a Global Social Service Network for Better Quality of Webservice Discovery

Author: Wuhui Chen, Incheon Paik, and Patrick C.K Hung

Year: 2013

Explanation:

Web services have had a tremendous impact on the Web for supporting a distributed service-based economy on a global scale. However, despite the outstanding progress, their uptake on a Web scale has been significantly less than initially anticipated. The isolation of services and the lack of social relationships among related services have been identified as reasons for the poor uptake. Connecting the isolated service islands into a global social service network to enhance the services' sociability on a global scale. First, link social service-specific principles based on linked data principles for publishing services on the open Web as linked social services; then, we suggest a new framework for constructing the global social service network following linked social service-specific principles based on complex network theories. Next, an approach is to enable the exploitation of the global social service network, providing Linked Social Services as a Service. Finally, experimental results show that our approach can solve the quality of service discovery problem, improving both the service discovering time and the success rate by exploring service-to-service based on the global social service network.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 Existing system

It is the nature of social media that makes people put more content, including photos, over OSNs without too much thought on the content. However, once something, such as a photo, is posted online, it becomes a permanent record, which may be used for purposes we never expect. For example, a posted photo in a party may reveal a connection of a celebrity to a mafia world. Because OSN users may be careless in posting content while the effect is so far-reaching, privacy protection over OSNs becomes an important issue. When more functions such as photo sharing and tagging are added, the situation becomes more complicated. For instance, nowadays we can share any photo as we like on OSNs, regardless of whether this photo contains other people (is a co-photo) or not.

3.1.1 Disadvantages

- ❖ Currently there is no restriction with sharing of co-photos.
- ❖ On the contrary, social network service providers like Facebook are encouraging users to post co-photos and tag there.
- ❖ Is it a privacy violation to share this co-photo without permission of the co-owners

3.2 Proposed System

In proposed system, to enhance the privacy admin verifies every user information which is stored in the database. Before giving the request, even user can match their profiles. So they can able to know their matches, likes and dislikes. The user can search the friend with his username, and also can send the friend request and also can response the request which has been sent by the other user. The user can form the group and can start chat with the group. In group chat, every user before joining the group can either accept or decline the group.

3.2.1 Advantages

- ❖ Online social networks help people to socialize with the world.
- ❖ Evaluation results show that privacy risk and data sharing loss are minimized by this approach
- ❖ To prevent possible privacy leakage of a photo, we design a mechanism to enable each individual in a photo be aware of the posting activity and participate in the decision making on the photo posting.

3.3 Feasibility Study

The feasibility of the project is analyzed in this phase and business proposal is put forth with a very general plan for the project and some cost estimates. During system analysis the feasibility study of the proposed system is to be carried out. This is to ensure that the proposed system is not a burden to the company. For feasibility analysis, some understanding of the major requirements for the system is essential.

Three key considerations involved in the feasibility analysis are :

1. ECONOMICAL FEASIBILITY
2. TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY
3. SOCIAL FEASIBILITY

3.3.1 Economical Feasibility

This study is carried out to check the economic impact that the system will have on the organization. The amount of fund that the company can pour into the research and development of the system is limited. The expenditures must be justified. Thus the developed system as well within the budget and this was achieved because most of the technologies used are freely available. Only the customized products had to be purchased.

3.3.2 Technical Feasibility

This study is carried out to check the technical feasibility, that is, the technical requirements of the system. Any system developed must not have a high demand on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands being placed on the client. The developed system must have a modest requirement, as only minimal or null changes are required for implementing this system.

3.3.3 Social Feasibility

The aspect of study is to check the level of acceptance of the system by the user. This includes the process of training the user to use the system efficiently. The user must not feel threatened by the system, instead must accept it as a necessity. The level of acceptance by the users solely depends on the methods that are employed to educate the user about the system and to make him familiar with it. His level of confidence must be raised so that he is also able to make some constructive criticism, which is welcomed, as he is the final user of the system.

CHAPTER 4
SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 System Architecture

Fig 4.1 System Architecture

4.2 Activity Diagram

Activity diagrams are graphical representations of workflows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency. In the UML, activity diagrams can be used to describe the business and operational step-by-step workflow of components in a system. It is an graphical representations of workflows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency.

Fig 4.2 Activity diagram

4.3 Use case Diagram

A use case diagram is a type of behavioral diagram created from a Use-case analysis. It is a set of scenarios that describing an interaction between a user and a system. A use case diagram displays the relationship among actors and use cases.

Fig 4.3 Use case diagram

4.4 Sequence Diagram

A sequence diagram shows, as parallel vertical lines (“lifelines”), different processes or objects that live simultaneously, and as the horizontal arrows, the messages exchanged between them, in the order in which they occur. This allows the specification of simple run time scenarios in a graphical manner.

Fig 4.4 Sequence diagram

4.5 Class Diagram

Class diagram is UML structure diagram which shows structure of the designed system at the level of classes and interfaces, shows their features constraints and relationships -associations, generalizations, dependencies, etc . A class diagram in the UML is a type of static structure diagram that describes the structure of a system by showing the system's classes, their attributes, and the relationships between the classes.

Fig 4.5 Class Diagram

4.6 Data flow Diagram

Data flow diagram is made up of a number of symbols, which represents system components. Most data flow modeling methods use four kinds of symbols. These symbols are used to represent four kinds of system components. Processes, data stores, data flows and external entities. Processes are represented by circles in DFD. A data flow diagram (DFD) is a graphical representation of the “flow” of data through an information system. It differs from the flowchart as it shows the data flow instead of the control flow of the program. A data flow diagram can also be used for the visualization of data processing.

4.6.1 Level 0

Fig 4.6 Data Flow Diagram–Level 0

4.6.2 Level 1

Fig 4.7 Data Flow Diagram–Level 1

4.6.3 Level 2

Fig 4.8 Data Flow Diagram–Level 2

4.6.4 Overall Data Flow Diagram

DFD consists of four major components: entities, processes, data stores and data flow. This DFD shows the relation between the admin and the users and all the details are stored in a database. User participate in the decision making of either accepting or declining the request.

Fig 4.9 Overall Data Flow Diagram

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 Introduction

The requirements specification is a technical specification of requirements for the software products. It is the first step in the requirements analysis process it lists the requirements of a particular software system including functional, performance and security requirements. The requirements also provide usage scenarios from a user, an operational and an administrative perspective. The purpose of software requirements specification is to provide a detailed overview of the software project, its parameters and goals. This describes the project target audience and its user interface, hardware and software requirements. It defines how the client, team and audience see the project and its functionality.

5.2 Hardware Requirements

- Processor : I3 and above.
- Speed : 2.2 GHZ
- RAM : 4 GB (min)
- Hard Disk : 250 GB

5.3 Software Requirements

- Operating system : Windows 10
- Technology Used : Asp.NET C#
- IDE : Microsoft Visual Studio 2012
- Database : Microsoft sql Server 2012

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 Software Description

6.1.1 .NET:

Microsoft .NET technology you will have access to a new generation of advanced software joining the best of computing and communications in a revolutionary new way. The effect will be to totally transform the Web and every other aspect of the computing experience. .NET enables developers, businesses, and consumers to harness technology on their terms.

6.1.2 Introduction to .NET

.NET will allow the creation of truly distributed Web services that will integrate and collaborate with a range of complementary services to help customers in ways that today's dotcoms can only dream of. The fundamental idea behind .NET is that the focus is shifting from individual Web sites or devices connected to the Internet to constellations of computers, devices, and services that work together to deliver broader, richer solutions. People will have control over how, when, and what information is delivered to them. Computers, devices and services will be able to collaborate with each other to provide rich services, instead of being isolated islands where the user provides the only integration.

Businesses will be able to offer their products and services in a way that lets customers seamlessly embed them in their own electronic fabric. Microsoft .NET will make computing and communicating simpler and easier than ever. It will spawn a new generation of Internet services, and enable tens of thousands of software developers to create revolutionary online services and businesses. It will put you back in control, and enable greater control of your privacy, digital identity, and data.

And software is what makes it all possible. However, Microsoft's .NET technology will only succeed if others adopt this new standard.

As mentioned on the .NET Framework page, .NET Framework is designed for cross-language compatibility. Cross-language compatibility means .NET components can interact with each other irrespective of the languages they are written in. An application written in VB .NET can reference a DLL file written in C# or a C# application can refer to a resource written in VC++, etc. This language interoperability extends to Object-Oriented inheritance. This cross-language compatibility is possible due to common language runtime. As you read on the .NET Framework page, when the .NET program is compiled, the output of the compiler is not an executable file but a file that contains a special type of code called the Microsoft Intermediate Language (MSIL). This MSIL is a low-level language which is designed to be read and understood by the common language runtime. Because all .NET executables exist as IL, they can freely operate.

The Common Language Specification defines the minimum standards that .NET language compilers must confirm to. Thus, any code compiled by a .NET compiler can interoperate with the .NET Framework. The Common Type System (CTS) defines the rules concerning data types and ensures that code is executed in a safe environment. Since all .NET applications are converted to IL before execution all primitive data types are represented as .NET types. This means that, a VB Integer and a C# integer are both represented in IL code as System.Int32. Because both the languages use a common type system, it is possible to transfer data between components and avoid time-consuming conversions.

6.1.3 Working of .NET

For those who are new to object-oriented programming, the concept of a class will be new to you. Simplistically, a class is the definition for a segment of code that can contain both data (called attributes) and functions (called methods).

The main method is passed as a parameter an array of strings (similar to the argv [] of C), and is declared as a static method.

.NET consists of two things :

- Programming language
- Platform

a) Cloud Computing

- Cloud computing is a style of computing in which dynamically scalable and often virtualized resources are provided as a service over the Internet.
- Users need not have knowledge of, expertise in, or control over the technology infrastructure in the "cloud" that supports them.
- The concept generally incorporates combinations of the following: • infrastructure as a service (IaaS) • platform as a service (PaaS) • software as a service (SaaS)
- Cloud computing customers do not generally own the physical infrastructure serving as host to the software platform in question. Instead, they avoid capital expenditure by renting usage from a third-party provider.
- They consume resources as a service and pay only for resources that they use.
- Many cloud-computing offerings employ the utility computing model, which is analogous to how traditional utility services (such as electricity) are consumed.

b) The C# programming language

C# is a high-level programming language that is all of the following:

- Simple
- Object-oriented
- Distributed
- Interpreted
- Robust
- Secure
- Architecture-neutral
- Portable
- High-performance
- Multithreaded
- Dynamic

The code and can bring about changes whenever felt necessary. Some of the standard needed to achieve the above-mentioned objectives are as follows:

C# is unusual in that each .NET program is both compiled and interpreted. With a compiler, you translate a Java program into an intermediate language called .NET byte codes – the platform independent codes interpreted by the .NET interpreter. With an interpreter, each byte code instruction is parsed and run on the

Fig.6.1 Program Execution Procedure

The Code Execution Process involves the following two stages:

1. Compiler time process.
2. Runtime process.

1. Compiler time process

1. The .NET framework has one or more language compilers, such as Visual Basic, C#, Visual C++, JScript, or one of many third-party compilers such as an Eiffel, Perl, or COBOL compiler.
2. Any one of the compilers translate your source code into Microsoft Intermediate Language (MSIL) code.

3. In short, VB.NET, C# and other language compilers generate MSIL code. (In other words, compiling translates your source code into MSIL and generates the required metadata.)
4. Currently "Microsoft Intermediate Language" (MSIL) code is also known as "Intermediate Language" (IL) Code or "Common Intermediate Language" (CIL) Code.

SOURCE CODE ----- .NET COMPILER -----> BYTE CODE (MSIL + META DATA)

2. Runtime process.

1. The Common Language Runtime (CLR) includes a JIT compiler for converting MSIL to native code.
2. The JIT Compiler in CLR converts the MSIL code into native machine code that is then executed by the OS.
3. During the runtime of a program the "Just in Time" (JIT) compiler of the Common Language Runtime (CLR) uses the Metadata and converts Microsoft Intermediate Language (MSIL) into native code.

BYTE CODE (MSIL + META DATA) ----- Just-In-Time (JIT) compiler ----
--> NATIVE CODE

Fig 6.2 Runtime Process

c) The .NET Platform

Language interoperability offers many benefits, for example, C#, Visual Basic .NET and Visual C++ .NET developers, for example, can work side-by-side on the same project without having to learn another programming language—all their code compiles into MSIL and links together to form one program. In addition, the .NET Framework can package old and new components to work together. This allows companies to reuse the code.

Fig 6.3 .NET Platform

6.1.4 Microsoft Visual Studio

Microsoft Visual Studio is an integrated development environment (IDE) from Microsoft. It is used to develop computer programs for Microsoft Windows, as well as web sites, web apps, web services and mobile apps. Visual Studio uses Microsoft software development platforms such as Windows API, Windows Forms, Windows Presentation Foundation, Windows Store and Microsoft Silverlight. It can produce both native code and managed code.

Visual Studio includes a code editor supporting IntelliSense (the code completion component) as well as code refactoring. The integrated debugger works both as a source-level debugger and a machine-level debugger. Other built-in tools include a code profiler, forms designer for building GUI applications, web designer, class designer, and database schema designer. It accepts plug-ins that

enhance the functionality at almost every level—including adding support for source control systems (like Subversion) and adding new toolsets like editors and visual designers for domain-specific languages or toolsets for other aspects of the software development lifecycle (like the Team Foundation Server client: Team Explorer).

Visual Studio supports 36 different programming languages and allows the code editor and debugger to support (to varying degrees) nearly any programming language, provided a language-specific service exists. Built-in languages include C, C++ and C++/CLI (via Visual C++), VB.NET (via Visual Basic .NET), C# (via Visual C#), F# (as of Visual Studio 2010) and Typescript (as of Visual Studio 2012 Update 2). Support for other languages such as Python, Ruby, Node.js, and M among others is available via language services installed separately. It also supports XML/XSLT, HTML/XHTML, JavaScript and CSS. Java (and J#) were supported in the past.

6.1.5 Microsoft SQL server

Microsoft SQL Server is a relational database management system developed by Microsoft. As a database server, it is a software product with the primary function of storing and retrieving data as requested by other software applications—which may run either on the same computer or on another computer across a network (including the Internet).

Microsoft markets at least a dozen different editions of Microsoft SQL Server, aimed at different audiences and for workloads ranging from small single-machine applications to large Internet-facing applications with many concurrent users.

a) Data Storage

Data storage is a database, which is a collection of tables with typed columns. SQL Server supports different data types, including primary types such as Integer, Float, Decimal, Char (including character strings), Varchar (variable length character strings), binary (for unstructured blobs of data), Text (for textual data) among others. The rounding of floats to integers uses either Symmetric Arithmetic Rounding or Symmetric Round Down (fix) depending on arguments.

Microsoft SQL Server also allows user-defined composite types (UDTs) to be defined and used. It also makes server statistics available as virtual tables and views (called Dynamic Management Views or DMVs). In addition to tables, a database can also contain other objects including views, stored procedures, indexes and constraints, along with a transaction log. A SQL Server database can contain a maximum of 2^{31} objects, and can span multiple OS-level files with a maximum file size of 2^{60} bytes (1 exabyte). The data in the database are stored in primary data files with an extension `.mdf`. Secondary data files, identified with a `.ndf` extension, are used to allow the data of a single database to be spread across more than one file, and optionally across more than one file system. Log files are identified with the `.ldf` extension.

Storage space allocated to a database is divided into sequentially numbered pages, each 8 KB in size. A page is the basic unit of I/O for SQL Server operations. A page is marked with a 96-byte header which stores metadata about the page including the page number, page type, free space on the page and the ID of the object that owns it. Page type defines the data contained in the page: data stored in the database, index, allocation map which holds information about how pages are allocated to tables and indexes, change map which holds information about the

changes made to other pages since last backup or logging, or contain large data types such as image or text. While page is the basic unit of an I/O operation, space is actually managed in terms of an extent which consists of 8 pages.

A database object can either span all 8 pages in an extent ("uniform extent") or share an extent with up to 7 more objects ("mixed extent"). A row in a database table cannot span more than one page, so is limited to 8 KB in size. However, if the data exceeds 8 KB and the row contains varchar or varbinary data, the data in those columns are moved to a new page (or possibly a sequence of pages, called an allocation unit) and replaced with a pointer to the data.

For physical storage of a table, its rows are divided into a series of partitions (numbered 1 to n). The partition size is user defined; by default all rows are in a single partition. A table is split into multiple partitions in order to spread a database over a computer cluster. Rows in each partition are stored in either B-tree or heap structure. If the table has an associated, clustered index to allow fast retrieval of rows, the rows are stored in-order according to their index values, with a B-tree providing the index. The data is in the leaf node of the leaves, and other nodes storing the index values for the leaf data reachable from the respective nodes. If the index is non-clustered, the rows are not sorted according to the index keys. An indexed view has the same storage structure as an indexed table. A table without a clustered index is stored in an unordered heap structure. However, the table may have non-clustered indices to allow fast retrieval of rows. In some situations the heap structure has performance advantages over the clustered structure. Both heaps and B-trees can span multiple allocation units.

b) Buffer management

SQL Server buffers pages in RAM to minimize disk I/O. Any 8 KB page can be buffered in-memory, and the set of all pages currently buffered is called the buffer

cache. The amount of memory available to SQL Server decides how many pages will be cached in memory. The buffer cache is managed by the Buffer Manager. Either reading from or writing to any page copies it to the buffer cache. Subsequent reads or writes are redirected to the in-memory copy, rather than the on-disc version. The page is updated on the disc by the Buffer Manager only if the in-memory cache has not been referenced for some time. While writing pages back to disc, asynchronous I/O is used whereby the I/O operation is done in a background thread so that other operations do not have to wait for the I/O operation to complete. Each page is written along with its checksum when it is written.

c) Concurrency and locking

SQL Server allows multiple clients to use the same database concurrently. As such, it needs to control concurrent access to shared data, to ensure data integrity— when multiple clients update the same data, or clients attempt to read data that is in the process of being changed by another client. SQL Server provides two modes of concurrency control: pessimistic concurrency and optimistic concurrency. When pessimistic concurrency control is being used, SQL Server controls concurrent access by using locks. Locks can be either shared or exclusive. Exclusive lock grants the user exclusive access to the data—no other user can access the data as long as the lock is held.

Locks can be applied on different levels of granularity—on entire tables, pages, or even on a per-row basis on tables. For indexes, it can either be on the entire index or on index leaves. The level of granularity to be used is defined on a per-database basis by the database administrator. While a fine-grained locking system allows more users to use the table or index simultaneously, it requires more

resources, so it does not automatically yield higher performance. SQL Server also includes two more lightweight mutual exclusion solutions—latches and spinlocks—which are less robust than locks but are less resource intensive. SQL Server uses them for DMVs and other resources that are usually not busy.

SQL Server monitors all worker threads that acquire locks to ensure that they do not end up in deadlocks—in case they do, SQL Server takes remedial measures, which in many cases are to kill one of the threads entangled in a deadlock and roll back the transaction it started. To implement locking, SQL Server contains the Lock Manager. The Lock Manager maintains an in-memory table that manages the database objects and locks, if any, on them along with other metadata about the lock. Access to any shared object is mediated by the lock manager, which either grants access to the resource or blocks it.

SQL Server also provides the optimistic concurrency control mechanism, which is similar to the multiversion concurrency control used in other databases. The mechanism allows a new version of a row to be created whenever the row is updated, as opposed to overwriting the row, i.e., a row is additionally identified by the ID of the transaction that created the version of the row. Both the old as well as the new versions of the row are stored and maintained, though the old versions are moved out of the database into a system database identified as Tempdb . When a row is in the process of being updated, any other requests are not blocked (unlike locking) but are executed on the older version of the row. If the other request is an update statement, it will result in two different versions of the rows—both of them will be stored by the database, identified by their respective transaction IDs.

6.1.6 SQL Server Management Studio

SQL Server Management Studio is a GUI tool included with SQL Server 2005 and later for configuring, managing, and administering all components within Microsoft SQL Server. The tool includes both script editors and graphical tools that work with objects and features of the server. SQL Server Management Studio replaces Enterprise Manager as the primary management interface for Microsoft SQL Server since SQL Server 2005.

A central feature of SQL Server Management Studio is the Object Explorer, which allows the user to browse, select, and act upon any of the objects within the server. SQL Server Management Studio can also be used to create a new database, alter any existing database schema by adding or modifying tables and indexes, or analyze performance.

6.1.7 Nonfunctional Requirements

a) Performance Requirements

The performance of this demo depends on executing this project on LAN or wifi communication channel. So we need to have one or more machine to execute the demo. Machine needs the enough hard disk space to install and run our project.

b) Safety Requirements

- The software may be safety-critical. If so, there are issues associated with its integrity level
- The software may not be safety-critical although it forms part of a safety-critical system. For example, software may simply log transactions.

- If a system must be of a high integrity level and if the software is shown to be of that integrity level, then the hardware must be at least of the same integrity level.

- There is little point in producing 'perfect' code in some language if hardware and system software (in widest sense) are not reliable.

- If a computer system is to run software of a high integrity level then that system should not at the same time accommodate software of a lower integrity level.

- Systems with different requirements for safety levels must be separated.

- Otherwise, the highest level of integrity required must be applied to all systems in the same environment.

c) Security Requirements

Do not block the some available ports through the windows firewall

Software Quality Attributes are :

Functionality: are the required functions available, including Interoperability and security.

Reliability: maturity, fault tolerance and recoverability

Usability: how easy it is to understand, learn, and operate the software System

Efficiency: performance and resource behavior.

Maintainability: Maintaining the software.

Portability: can the software easily be transferred to another environment,

6.2 List of Modules

- Enrollment
- Reform the account
- Itinerary Add
- Companion Appeal
- Contour Paired
- Protected Contour
- Association Operations

6.3 Module Description

6.3.1 Enrollment

If normal users who want to like together with peoples in this social site then, they can create an account on this site by executing registration process, means normal users provide basic details like user name, password, address, e-mail id and also phone number which will be later utilized for profile matching algorithm. After registration if the user want to access account then user must enter correct user name / e-mail id and password.

If credentials are correct then the server allows user to go into the websites or else user name or password alert is generated by server user to go into the websites or else user name or password alert is generated by server. Then according to the alert they have to change their corresponding details and according to that they can access easily inside the respective applications if they want to access.

6.3.2 Reform the account

After the login, user must want to update his / her own profile, because this is the key process for all of the other activities in a system. In that page user enter additional information`s like Interests, schooling information, college name, likes and, dislikes and so on and also select profile picture then click update profile which is useful for the purpose of identification.

After registration process one have update their profile picture then only it becomes easy for everyone to identify if he / she ant to add any information of their details about their school, college, his / her likes and dislikes. For example, in school or in college the students may be with same name in that case in this he can proceed with the details given by the person with another person. The process in which if he / she ants means enter the details of their personal or they may not also. He/ she can change their account also if they need. The main purpose is for the identification. If he want to add to anyone he may give the request.

6.3.3 Itinerary Add

User post some contents to share his / her feelings to other peoples by means of sharing within the friends lists. If anyone tags your own profile on some posts, user will receive a notification regarding that post. With user interest he/she can accept or decline the post, before that it is viewed by anyone in their friends list. If user decline the request sent by another user that post cannot be viewed by anyone on their friends list. If they wish they can share the information or they can share the photos here tagging becomes more complicated issue nowadays.

If someone post a photo the same photo that has been posted by someone then the photo that has posted by the person before must receive the notification that someone has posted your photo that nobody can vie their notification in their in the friends list. The photo that has been posted by anybody can view the post that can be viewed by nobody. The photo that has been posted by someone can be tag by anyone those who are involved in the corresponding application.

6.3.4 Companion Appeal

User enter some of the string into the search bar and then send this string as request to the server. When user receive these type of requests then server automatically check the possibility of results and then response to the requested user. This response has only name of the persons, does not contain another information. If user want to be a friend with any member from the list then select the necessary parameters and then send friend request. For example, he/she has to send the request then another person has to give the response. If anyone has accepted he / she can involve in their corresponding application.

The details or the information of the person is stored in the server database if the user send the request to the server the server itself has the request then the server ill match with the corresponding details of the people then the server will send the response the person who had send the request ill get the response and then he can ant means he can add to the particular application. The person can add another person in his / her friends list thus he can chat with the person if he does not like then the person can reject.

6.3.5 Contour Paired

Whenever a user give a friend requests then this module will be executed by server automatically. Server initially get the another user name and profile

information's from database and also collect profile details of requested users. After that server matches both the profiles with specified five parameters by using profile matching algorithm, this process is known as profile matching. Finally generate a single value based on five parameter matching. Request Received user view friends requests information's with this profile value. Based on this user may be accept the request, may be reject the request the details that has to be match with to persons this can be done by profile matching. Accept or reject depends upon the person if he / she interested in the particular event.

6.3.6 Protected Contour

Any user can upload their own image or some images as their profile picture for the public view and to interact with their friends with unique identification. If anyone, uploads the same profile picture like another user, will send a notification to the particular user who uploaded the image first and hence identified. With the permission of that user, image will be viewed or else admin will block that user.

6.3.7 Association Operations

Users can able to create group for sharing information with in specified users, then server automatically create group to start chatting. With the permission of every individual in that group you were added by group admin. Every individual will get a notification regarding the participation of that group. If they interested to add in that group they accept the notification or else that person won't be in that group if they decline the request. Accepting and declining the request is completely based on user's wish.

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 Introduction

Testing is a process of executing a program with the intent of finding an error. A good test case is one that has a high probability of finding an as-yet – undiscovered error. System testing is the stage of implementation, which is aimed at ensuring that the system works accurately and efficiently as expected before live operation commences. It verifies that the whole set of programs hang together. System testing requires a test consists of several key activities and steps for run program, string, system and is important in adopting a successful new system. .

The software testing process commences once the program is created and the documentation and related data structures are designed. Software testing is essential for correcting errors. Otherwise the program or the project is not said to be complete. Software testing is the critical element of software quality assurance and represents the ultimate the review of specification design and coding. Testing is the process of executing the program with the intent of finding the error. A good test case design is one that as a probability of finding an yet undiscovered error.

7.2 Levels of Testing

The various levels of testing are:

1. Unit Testing
2. Functional Testing
3. Performance Testing
4. Stress Testing
5. Structure Testing

7.2.1 Unit Testing

Unit testing is conducted to verify the functional performance of each modular component of the software. Unit testing focuses on the smallest unit of the software design (i.e.), the module. The white-box testing techniques were heavily employed for unit testing.

7.2.2 Functional Testing

Functional testing cases involved exercising the code with nominal input values for which the expected results are known, as well as boundary values and special values, such as logically related inputs, files of identical elements, and empty files.

7.2.3 Performance Testing

It determines the amount of execution time spent in various parts of the unit, program throughput, and response time and device utilization by the program unit.

7.2.4 Stress Testing

Stress Test is those test designed to intentionally break the unit. A Great deal can be learned about the strength and limitations of a program by examining the manner in which a programmer in which a program unit breaks.

7.2.5 Structured Testing

Structured Tests are concerned with exercising the internal logic of a program and traversing particular execution paths. The way in which White-Box test strategy was employed to ensure that the test cases could Guarantee that all independent paths within a module have been have been exercised at least once.

- Exercise all logical decisions on their true or false sides.
- Execute all loops at their boundaries and within their operational bounds.
- Exercise internal data structures to assure their validity.
- Checking attributes for their correctness.
- Handling end of file condition, I/O errors, buffer problems and textual errors in output information

7.2.5 Integration Testing

Integration testing is a systematic technique for construction the program structure while at the same time conducting tests to uncover errors associated with interfacing. i.e., integration testing is the complete testing of the set of modules which makes up the product. The objective is to take untested modules and build a program structure tester should identify critical modules.

Critical modules should be tested as early as possible. One approach is to wait until all the units have passed testing, and then combine them and then tested. This approach is evolved from unstructured testing of small programs. Another strategy is to construct the product in increments of tested units. A small set of modules are integrated together and tested, to which another module is added and tested in combination. And so on. The advantages of this approach are that, interface dispenses can be easily found and corrected.

The major error that was faced during the project is linking error. When all the modules are combined the link is not set properly with all support files. Then we checked out for interconnection and the links. Errors are localized to the new module and its intercommunications. The product development can be staged, and modules integrated in as they complete unit testing. Testing is completed when the last module is integrated and tested.

7.3 Testing Techniques

Testing is a process of executing a program with the intent of finding an error. A good test case is one that has a high probability of finding an as-yet – undiscovered error. A successful test is one that uncovers an as-yet- undiscovered error. System testing is the stage of implementation, which is aimed at ensuring that the system works accurately and efficiently as expected before live operation commences.

7.3.1 White Box Testing

This testing is also called as Glass box testing. In this testing, by knowing the specific functions that a product has been design to perform test can be conducted that demonstrate each function is fully operational at the same time searching for errors in each function. It is a test case design method that uses the control structure of the procedural design to derive test cases. Basis path testing is a white box testing.

- Flow graph notation
- Cyclometric complexity
- Deriving test cases
- Graph matrices Control

7.3.2 Black Box Testing

In this testing by knowing the internal operation of a product, test can be conducted to ensure that “all gears mesh”, that is the internal operation performs according to specification and all internal components have been adequately exercised. It fundamentally focuses on the functional requirements of the software.

The steps involved in black box test case design are:

- Graph based testing methods
- Equivalence partitioning
- Boundary value analysis
- Comparison testing

7.3.3 Program Testing

The logical and syntax errors have been pointed out by program testing. A syntax error is an error in a program statement that in violates one or more rules of the language in which it is written. An improperly defined field dimension or omitted keywords are common syntax error. These errors are shown through error messages generated by the computer. A logic error on the other hand deals with the incorrect data fields, out-off-range items and invalid combinations. Since the compiler s will not deduct logical error, the programmer must examine the output. Condition testing exercises the logical conditions contained in a module.

The possible types of elements in a condition include a Boolean operator, Boolean variable, a pair of Boolean parentheses A relational operator or on arithmetic expression. Condition testing method focuses on testing each condition in the program the purpose of condition test is to deduct not only errors in the condition of a program but also other a errors in the program.

7.3.4 Security Testing

Security testing attempts to verify the protection mechanisms built in to a system well, in fact, protect it from improper penetration.

7.3.5 Validation Testing

At the culmination of integration testing, software is completely assembled as a package. Interfacing errors have been uncovered and corrected and a final series of software test-validation testing begins. Validation testing can be defined in many ways, but a simple definition is that validation succeeds when the software functions in manner that is reasonably expected by the customer. Software validation is achieved through a series of black box tests that demonstrate conformity with requirement. After validation test has been conducted, one of two conditions exists.

- The function or performance characteristics confirm to specifications and are accepted.
- A validation from specification is uncovered and a deficiency created.

Deviation or errors discovered at this step in this project is corrected prior to completion of the project with the help of the user by negotiating to establish a method for resolving deficiencies. Thus the proposed system under consideration has been tested by using validation testing and found to be working satisfactorily. Though there were deficiencies in the system they were not catastrophic.

7.3.6 User Acceptance Testing

User acceptance of the system is key factor for the success of any system. The system under consideration is tested for user acceptance by constantly keeping in touch with prospective system and user at the time of developing and making changes whenever required via input and output screen.

CHAPTER 8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To enhance the privacy, admin verifies every user information which is stored in the database. Before giving the request, every user can match their profiles. So they can able to know their matches, likes and dislikes. The user can search the friend with his username, and also can send the friend request and also response the request which has been sent by the other user. The user can form the group and can start chat with the group. In group chat, every user before joining the group they can either accept or decline the group.

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

9.1 Conclusion

Information sharing is one of the most popular feature in online social networks such as Facebook. Unfortunately, careless photo posting may reveal privacy of individuals in a posted photo. To curb the privacy leakage, we proposed to enable individuals potentially in a photo to give the permissions before posting a co-photo. We expect that our proposed scheme be very useful in protecting users' privacy in photo/image sharing over online social networks.

9.2 Future Enhancement

The future enhancement of this project is to be a face detection, it is based upon the training of a classifier using number of positive images that represent the object to be recognized and even large number of negative images that represent objects or feature not to be detected. The photo x is provided in which I faces are detected. This technique can be adapted to accurately detect facial features. The area of the image is regionalized containing the highest probability of the feature so as to analyze the facial feature. By doing this, the speed of the detection is increased as it eliminates the false positive which reduces the area to be examined.

APPENDICES

A. Sample code

User Register

```
<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true"
CodeFile="UserRegister.aspx.cs" Inherits="UserRegister" %>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
```

```
<html lang="zxx">
```

```
<head>
```

```
<title>Profile Matching</title>
```

```
<!--meta tags -->
```

```
<meta charset="UTF-8">
```

```
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-
scale=1"><meta name="keywords" content="Beaut Responsive web template,
Bootstrap
```

Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template, Smartphone
Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung,

LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design"

```
/><script>
```

```
addEventListener("load", function () {
setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);
```

```
    }, false);

    function hideURLbar() {
        window.scrollTo(0, 1);
    }
}
```

Friends Search

```
<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true"
CodeFile="FriendsSearch.aspx.cs" Inherits="FriendsSearch" %>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
```

```
<html lang="zxx">
```

```
<head>
```

```
<title>Profile Matching</title>
```

```
<!--meta tags -->
```

```
<meta charset="UTF-8">
```

```
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-
scale=1"><meta name="keywords" content="Beaut Responsive web template,
Bootstrap
```

```
Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template, Smartphone
Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung,
```

```
LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />
```

```
using System;
```

```
using System.Collections.Generic;
```

```

using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Configuration;
using System.Data;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

public partial class FriendsSearch : System.Web.UI.Page
{

    protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)

    {

        if (Session["UserName"] != null && Session["UserMailID"] !=
        null) {

            TextBox1.Text = Session["UserName"].ToString();
            TextBox2.Text = Session["UserMailID"].ToString();
            TextBox24.Text = Session["PMID"].ToString();
        }
    }
}

```

Friends Request

```

<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true"
CodeFile="FriendsRequest.aspx.cs" Inherits="FriendsRequest" %>

```

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
```

```
<html lang="zxx">
```

```
<head>
```

```
<title>Profile Matching</title>
```

```
<!--meta tags -->
```

```
<meta charset="UTF-8">
```

```
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-  
scale=1"><meta name="keywords" content="Beaut Responsive web template,  
Bootstrap
```

Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template, Smartphone
Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung,

LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design"

```
/></script>
```

```
addEventListener("load", function () {  
    setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);  
}, false);
```

```
function hideURLbar() {  
    window.scrollTo(0, 1);  
  
}
```

```
</script>
```

using System;

```

using System.Collections.Generic;

using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Configuration;
using System.Data;

using System.Data.SqlClient;
public partial class FriendsRequest : System.Web.UI.Page
{
    protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        if (Session["UserName"] != null && Session["UserMailID"] !=
        null) {

            TextBox1.Text = Session["UserName"].ToString();
            TextBox2.Text = Session["UserMailID"].ToString();
            TextBox24.Text = Session["PMID"].ToString();

        }
        if(!Page.IsPostBack)
        {

            request();

        }
    }
}

```

Add Post

```
<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true"
CodeFile="AddPosts.aspx.cs" Inherits="AddPosts" %>
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Configuration;

using System.Data;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

public partial class AddPosts : System.Web.UI.Page
{
    protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        if (Session["UserName"] != null && Session["UserMailID"] !=
null) {

            TextBox1.Text = Session["UserName"].ToString();
            TextBox2.Text = Session["UserMailID"].ToString();
            TextBox24.Text = Session["PMID"].ToString();
        }
    }
}
```

```
}  
}
```

Create Groups

```
<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true"  
CodeFile="CreateGroups.aspx.cs" Inherits="CreateGroups" %>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
```

```
<html lang="zxx">
```

```
<head>
```

```
<title>Profile Matching</title>
```

```
<!--meta tags -->
```

```
<meta charset="UTF-8">
```

```
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-  
scale=1"><meta name="keywords" content="Beaut Responsive web template,  
Bootstrap
```

Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template,

Smartphone Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung, LG,
SonyEricsson, Motorola web design" />

```
<script>
```

```
addEventListener("load", function () {
```

```
setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);
```

```
    }, false);

    function hideURLbar() {
        window.scrollTo(0, 1);
    }

</script>
```

View All Request

```
<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true"
CodeFile="UserRequests.aspx.cs" Inherits="UserRequests" %>
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="zxx">
  <head>

    <title>Profile Matching</title>
    <!--meta tags -->
    <meta charset="UTF-8">

    <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-
scale=1"><meta name="keywords" content="Beaut Responsive web template,
Bootstrap
```

Web Templates, Flat Web Templates, Android Compatible web template, Smartphone
Compatible web template, free webdesigns for Nokia, Samsung,

LG, SonyEricsson, Motorola web design"

```
 /><script>  
  
    addEventListener("load", function () {  
        setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);  
    }, false);  
  
    function hideURLbar() {  
        window.scrollTo(0, 1);  
    }  
</script>
```

B. Screenshots

Home

User Register

User Login

Admin Login

User Details

User Report

Matching Information

Friends Search

Post

Group

User Request

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